

Corrosion of 3S Aluminium in the Mixture of Acid Solutions

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Corrosion of aluminium has been studied in hydrochloric acid, tartaric acid, citric acid and their mixture with sodium hydroxide¹. Corrosion resistance of aluminium in sulphuric acid has also been studied². In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the corrosivity of aluminium manganese alloy in mineral acids and their mixtures.

Experimental :

Aluminium specimen had the following composition: Al-98% Max., Cu -0.15% Max., Mn-1%, Fe-0.75% and Si-0.6%. It was 3S_{1/2}, hard (22 S. W. G.). Rectangular specimens of size 3×6 cm were used. Preparation, testing procedure and cleaning of the specimen were same as described earlier³. 250 ml of the solution was used for immersion of each specimen. All experiments were carried out at 32°±1°. Duration of the experiment was 2 days. In the case of mixtures the total normality of the solution was 1 N in all the cases. Results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion :

(i) Mixture of hydrochloric acid and nitric acid :

Hydrochloric acid alone is highly corrosive to aluminium, the corrosivity increasing with increase

Coupons : 3×6 cm Concentration of acids (Normality)	Temp. 32±1°C	Duration : 2 days	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	H ₃ PO ₄	HNO ₃
0.1			48.1	12.2	32.4	10.6
0.2			363	12.9	45.6	11.5
0.4			1250	14.4	64.1	14.1
0.5			1406	15.1	71.6	14.2
0.6			1425	16.1	80.3	15.7
0.8			1950	17.2	92.2	17.0
0.9			2054	17.7	92.8	18.3
1.0			2320	18.0	98.0	18.5

in the concentration. Compared to hydrochloric acid, nitric acid is mildly corrosive, the extent of corrosion increasing slightly with increase in concentration.

The mixtures of hydrochloric acid and nitric acid are much less corrosive than the sum of the individual acids at their respective concentrations. The nitric acid retards the corrosivity of the hydrochloric acid.

(ii) Mixture of hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid :

Like nitric acid, sulphuric acid is also mildly corrosive to aluminium. Addition of sulphuric acid to hydrochloric acid accelerates corrosivity of hydrochloric acid. At the intermediate concentration

TABLE 2. CORROSION OF 3S ALUMINIUM IN MIXED ACID

Coupons : 3×6 Cm. Concentration of mixture (Normality)	Temp. 32±1°C			Duration : 2 days			(loss mg)
A+B	A→HCl +	HCl +	HCl +	H ₃ PO ₄ +	H ₂ SO ₄ +	H ₃ PO ₄ +	H ₃ PO ₄ +
	B→HNO ₃	H ₂ SO ₄	H ₃ PO ₄	H ₂ SO ₄	HNO ₃	HNO ₃	HNO ₃
1.0+0.0	2320	2320	2320	98.0	18.0		98.0
0.9+0.1	91.6	2370	2390	64.8	18.8		86.5
0.8+0.2	26.2	2440	2420	60.3	19.3		74.4
0.6+0.4	22.0	2400	2480	37.2	19.4		62.6
0.5+0.5	20.5	2390	2260	34.3	19.2		53.0
0.4+0.6	20.0	2100	1830	29.2	19.0		44.8
0.2+0.8	19.5	400	1570	21.5	18.8		26.8
0.1+0.9	19.0	165	1560	18.5	18.6		24.3
0.0+1.0	18.5	18	98	18.0	18.5		18.5

(i. e. 0.4 to 0.6 *N*) of sulphuric acid, acceleration of corrosion is about 70%.

Overall corrosion due to mixture of acids is greater than the sum of the corrosion due to individual component of the mixture.

(iii) *Mixture of hydrochloric acid and phosphoric acid :*

Compared to nitric acid and sulphuric acid phosphoric acid is more corrosive; its corrosivity, however, is much less than that of hydrochloric acid. Addition of phosphoric acid accelerates overall corrosion. Corrosive tendency is nearly that of the sulphuric- hydrochloric acid mixtures. At very low concentration of chloride ions the increase in corrosivity is tremendous.

(iv) *Mixture of phosphoric acid and sulphuric acid :*

Phosphoric acid is more corrosive than sulphuric acid. The corrosivity of the mixture of sulphuric acid and phosphoric acid is not additive; the actual corrosion is about 50% or less than the total corrosion due to individual acids at their respective concentrations. Sulphuric acid which accelerates the corrosivity of hydrochloric acid, retards the corrosivity of phosphoric acid. The percentage inhibition of the corrosion of phosphoric acid due to sulphuric acid increases with increase in concentration of the latter, the maximum and minimum inhibition observed being 56 and 30% respectively.

(v) *Mixture of sulphuric acid and nitric acid :*

Both these acids, individually, are mildly corrosive to aluminium compared to hydrochloric acid and phosphoric acid. The mixture of sulphuric acid and nitric acid is slightly more corrosive than the individual acids; the overall corrosion being about 60% of the sum of the individual acids.

(vi) *Mixture of phosphoric acid and nitric acid :*

The mixture of phosphoric acid and nitric acid is less corrosive than the individual acids at their respective concentrations. Nitric acid retards the corrosion due to phosphoric acid, the decrease in corrosion, in general, increases with increase in concentration of the nitric acid, the maximum inhibition observed is about 39%.

In pure acids the corrosion rate increases with increase in concentration of the acids. The corrosivity of the acids is in the following order :

the corrosivity of last two acids being practically of the same order. Among the mixtures, the corrosivity,

in general, is in the following order :

If the corrosion is to be governed by the sum of the corrosion values of the individual acids at their appropriate concentrations, the order of corrosivity of the mixtures should be

The change in the order of corrosivity is found only in the mixtures involving nitric acid. Nitric acid inhibits corrosion of highly corrosive acid (hydrochloric acid) to a greater extent than the less corrosive acid (phosphoric acid). This is contrary to the fact that in the presence of chloride ions it is difficult to bring about efficient decrease in corrosion because the oxide film formed by nitric acid on the metal surface is easily penetrable by chloride ions. Further, phosphoric acid is less corrosive than the hydrochloric acid. Nitric acid should protect aluminium better in phosphoric acid as it can form a protective film of phosphate over its surface in addition to the oxide film formed by nitric acid.

It is difficult to assign any definite mechanism to account for the behaviour of the mixtures $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 + \text{HNO}_3$ and $\text{HCl} + \text{HNO}_3$; it may be that a mixed film of oxide and phosphate on aluminium surface is not very protective than a pure oxide film which protects the metal even in presence of highly active chloride ions. It can be concluded that corrosivity of aluminium in the mixture of mineral acids is not additive but depends upon the nature of anions.

The behaviour is also remarkable in the mixtures $\text{HCl} + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and $\text{HCl} + \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$ where the corrosion observed is sometimes much higher than the sum of the corrosion of the individual acids at their respective concentrations.

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